

Columnar Cell Lesions and Flat Epithelial Atypia in Mastectomy Specimens: An Institution Based Study in Bihar

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Abstract:

Background: Columnar cell lesions (CCLs) and flat epithelial atypia (FEA) are proliferative breast lesions that may serve as precursors to breast carcinoma. Their clinical significance lies in their potential to progress to malignancy, necessitating accurate diagnosis and appropriate management. This study aims to evaluate the prevalence and characteristics of CCLs and FEA in mastectomy specimens from a North Indian population and to analyze their association with various clinicopathological factors.

Methods: A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted on 54 mastectomy specimens. Data were collected from medical records, including patient demographics and histopathological findings. Histopathological slides were reviewed for CCLs and FEA by two independent pathologists. Data analysis was performed using SPSS version 21.0, employing descriptive statistics, Chi-square tests, and t-tests.

Results: Columnar cell lesions were identified in 27.8% of the specimens, and flat epithelial atypia was observed in 22.2% of the cases. The mean tumor size was significantly larger in cases with CCLs (3.6 ± 1.0 cm) compared to those without CCLs (3.0 ± 1.1 cm, $p = 0.03$). Similarly, specimens with FEA had a larger mean tumor size (3.5 ± 1.0 cm) compared to those without FEA (3.0 ± 1.1 cm, $p = 0.04$). No statistically significant correlation was found between histopathological types and the presence of these lesions.

Conclusion: The study found a notable prevalence of CCLs and FEA in mastectomy specimens, with larger tumor sizes significantly associated with the presence of these lesions. This emphasizes the importance of thorough histopathological evaluation in mastectomy specimens to identify precursor lesions with potential prognostic and therapeutic implications.

Recommendations: Further research is needed to elucidate the biological behavior of CCLs and FEA and to refine diagnostic criteria. The integration of molecular techniques could enhance diagnostic precision and contribute to better clinical outcomes.

Keywords: Columnar Cell Lesions, Flat Epithelial Atypia, Breast Carcinoma, Mastectomy Specimens, Histopathology.

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Introduction

Columnar cell lesions (CCLs) and flat epithelial atypia (FEA) are two types of proliferative breast lesions that have garnered significant attention in recent years due to their potential role as precursors to breast carcinoma. These lesions are characterized by the presence of columnar epithelial cells lining the terminal ductal lobular units, often with accompanying architectural and cytological atypia. Although initially considered benign, emerging evidence suggests that CCLs and FEA may represent early stages in the development of certain types of breast cancer, particularly low-grade ductal carcinoma in situ (DCIS) and invasive ductal carcinoma [1].

The clinical significance of CCLs and FEA lies in their potential to progress to malignancy, necessitating accurate diagnosis and appropriate management. Recent studies have demonstrated that the presence of these lesions in breast biopsy specimens correlates with an increased risk of subsequent breast cancer development, particularly when they exhibit atypical features [2]. Consequently, understanding the prevalence and pathological characteristics of CCLs and FEA in mastectomy specimens is crucial for developing effective surveillance and treatment strategies.

Despite the recognized importance of these lesions, there remains considerable variability in their diagnosis and interpretation. Histopathological

evaluation remains the gold standard for identifying CCLs and FEA, but inter-observer variability can pose challenges in achieving consistent and accurate diagnoses [3]. This variability underscores the need for standardized diagnostic criteria and the integration of adjunctive molecular techniques to enhance diagnostic precision.

Recent advances in molecular pathology have provided new insights into the biological underpinnings of CCLs and FEA. Studies have identified recurrent genetic alterations in these lesions, including mutations in the PIK3CA gene and loss of heterozygosity at key chromosomal loci, which mirror changes observed in more advanced breast cancers [4]. These findings support the notion that CCLs and FEA are part of a continuum of breast neoplasia, highlighting their potential role as early markers of malignant transformation.

This study aims to evaluate the presence of columnar cell lesions (CCLs) and flat epithelial atypia (FEA) in mastectomy specimens

Methodology

Study Design: This is a descriptive cross-sectional study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at Anugrah Narayan Magadh Medical College and Hospital, Gaya, Bihar. The study was conducted over a period of eight months, from January 2023 to August 2023.

Participants: A total of 54 mastectomy specimens were included in this study. The participants were selected based on the following inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Inclusion Criteria

- Female patients who underwent mastectomy for breast carcinoma.
- Patients with complete clinical and histopathological records.
- Specimens with adequate tissue for evaluation of CCLs and FEA.

Exclusion Criteria

- Incomplete medical records or inadequate tissue samples.
- Mastectomy specimens from patients with prior neoadjuvant therapy.
- Specimens with extensive tumor necrosis precluding evaluation of surrounding non-tumor tissue.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, all eligible mastectomy specimens during the study period were included. Histopathological evaluations were conducted blindly by two independent pathologists to reduce observer bias.

Data Collection: Data were collected from medical records, including patient demographics, clinical history, and histopathological findings. Histopathological slides of mastectomy specimens were reviewed for the presence of CCLs and FEA.

Procedure: Mastectomy specimens were fixed in 10% formalin, embedded in paraffin, sectioned at 3-4 microns, and stained with Hematoxylin and Eosin (H&E). Two independent pathologists examined the slides for CCLs and FEA using light microscopy. Discrepancies were resolved through joint review and consensus. Findings were recorded in a structured format, noting the presence and characteristics of CCLs and FEA.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 21.0. Descriptive statistics, including frequencies and percentages, were used to summarize categorical variables. Continuous variables were summarized using means and standard deviations. Associations between variables were assessed using Chi-square tests for categorical data and t-tests for continuous data. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Result

The study included 54 mastectomy specimens from female patients with a mean age of 52.3 ± 10.2 years. The distribution of demographic and clinical characteristics is summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics

Characteristic	n (%)
Age (years)	52.3 ± 10.2
Tumor Size (cm)	3.2 ± 1.1
Histopathological Type	
- Invasive Ductal Carcinoma	40 (74.1%)
- Invasive Lobular Carcinoma	10 (18.5%)
- Other Types	4 (7.4%)

Out of the 54 mastectomy specimens, columnar cell lesions were identified in 15 (27.8%) cases, and flat epithelial atypia was observed in 12 (22.2%) cases. The prevalence data is shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Prevalence of CCLs and FEA in Mastectomy Specimens

Lesion Type	n (%)
Columnar Cell Lesions (CCLs)	15 (27.8%)
Flat Epithelial Atypia (FEA)	12 (22.2%)

The association between tumor size and the presence of CCLs and FEA was evaluated. The mean tumor size was significantly larger in cases with CCLs (3.6 ± 1.0 cm) compared to those without CCLs (3.0 ± 1.1 cm, $p = 0.03$). Similarly,

specimens with FEA had a larger mean tumor size (3.5 ± 1.0 cm) compared to those without FEA (3.0 ± 1.1 cm, $p = 0.04$). These findings are detailed in Table 3.

Table 3: Association between Tumor Size and Presence of Lesions

Lesion Type	Present (n = 27)	Absent (n = 27)	p-value
CCLs	3.6 ± 1.0 cm	3.0 ± 1.1 cm	0.03
FEA	3.5 ± 1.0 cm	3.0 ± 1.1 cm	0.04

The correlation between histopathological types and the presence of CCLs and FEA was also analyzed. Invasive ductal carcinoma cases had a higher prevalence of CCLs (30%) and FEA (25%) compared to other types, but these differences were not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$).

Table 4: Correlation between Histopathological Types and Lesion Presence

Histopathological Type	CCLs		FEA	
	Present	Absent	Present	Absent
Invasive Ductal Carcinoma	12 (30%)	28 (70%)	10 (25%)	30 (75%)
Invasive Lobular Carcinoma	2 (20%)	8 (80%)	1 (10%)	9 (90%)
Other Types	1 (25%)	3 (75%)	1 (25%)	3 (75%)

Discussion

The study examined the prevalence and associations of columnar cell lesions (CCLs) and flat epithelial atypia (FEA) in mastectomy specimens from 54 female patients treated at Anugrah Narayan Magadh Medical College and Hospital, Gaya, Bihar, over an eight-month period from January 2023 to August 2023. The average age of the participants was 52.3 years, and the majority of the cases (74.1%) were invasive ductal carcinoma.

Columnar cell lesions were identified in 27.8% of the specimens, while flat epithelial atypia was present in 22.2% of the cases. This notable prevalence underscores the significance of these lesions in mastectomy specimens, suggesting that both CCLs and FEA are relatively common findings in patients undergoing mastectomy for breast carcinoma.

The study revealed a significant association between larger tumor size and the presence of CCLs and FEA. Specifically, the mean tumor size was significantly larger in cases with CCLs (3.6 cm) compared to those without (3.0 cm), with a similar trend observed for FEA (3.5 cm versus 3.0 cm). This suggests that larger tumors may be more likely to exhibit these precursor lesions, which could indicate a more advanced or aggressive disease state requiring closer monitoring and potentially different management strategies.

Although invasive ductal carcinoma cases had a higher prevalence of CCLs (30%) and FEA (25%) compared to other histopathological types, these differences were not statistically significant. This indicates that while there may be a trend towards higher occurrence of these lesions in invasive ductal carcinoma, further studies with larger sample sizes are needed to confirm these findings.

Overall, the study highlights the considerable prevalence of CCLs and FEA in mastectomy specimens and their association with larger tumor sizes. These findings emphasize the importance of meticulous histopathological evaluation in mastectomy specimens to identify these lesions, which could have significant prognostic and therapeutic implications. Future research should focus on understanding the biological significance of CCLs and FEA in breast carcinoma to better inform clinical practice.

Bhat et al. (2018) examined the morphology of CCLs and other changes in surgical biopsy specimens over two years. They found that a spectrum of precursor lesions, including CCLs, was commonly seen. Accurate diagnosis of these lesions was emphasized for early detection and proper management [5].

LakshmiPriya et al. (2021) documented the extent and pattern of CCLs and other proliferative breast lesions in mastectomy specimens. They found that 33.3% of cases had CCLs. The study did not find a statistically significant relationship between

proliferative breast lesions and tumor grade, stage, nodal status, or menopausal status [6]. SurekhaVijayan et al. (2019) analyzed excision biopsy specimens and found that CCLs were frequently seen alongside invasive ductal carcinoma (IDC). The presence of CCLs was associated with low-grade ductal carcinoma in situ (DCIS) and atypical ductal hyperplasia (ADH) [7].

Chagas et al. (2022) reported on a case of managing B3 lesions, highlighting the complexity and necessity of multidisciplinary evaluation for accurate diagnosis and management. The patient underwent multiple biopsies and surgeries, demonstrating the importance of thorough pathological assessment [8]. Jaffar et al. (2023) studied 286 biopsy specimens, finding that 3.84% had FEA. DCIS showed 100% positivity for FEA, followed by fibrocystic disease (62%) and IDC (15%). The study emphasized the association of FEA with other breast lesions [9].

Logullo and Nimir (2019) provided a review of CCLs, discussing their histologic diagnostic criteria, molecular alterations, and clinical implications. They highlighted the significance of FEA as a non-obligate pre-neoplastic lesion [10]. Srour et al. (2020) found that pure FEA on core needle biopsy was upstaged to cancer in only 2.9% of cases. The study suggested that excisional biopsy may not be necessary for pure FEA and could be managed with close imaging surveillance [11].

Conclusion

This study found a notable prevalence of columnar cell lesions (27.8%) and flat epithelial atypia (22.2%) in mastectomy specimens. Larger tumor sizes were significantly associated with the presence of these lesions. While invasive ductal carcinoma cases exhibited higher occurrences of CCLs and FEA, no statistically significant correlation was found between histopathological types and the presence of these lesions. These results highlight the importance of thorough histopathological evaluation of mastectomy specimens to identify precursor lesions such as CCLs and FEA, which may have implications for patient prognosis and management.

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